

The Fundamental Templates of Quality Ads: Relevance in Contemporary Digital Advertising

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Abstract:

recall in a competitive media environment. While creativity in advertising is often perceived as unpredictable, research suggests that successful advertisements frequently follow identifiable structural patterns known as creativity templates. The framework proposed by Goldenberg, Mazursky, and Solomon identifies six fundamental templates that commonly appear in effective advertising campaigns.

The present study examines the relevance of these creativity templates in contemporary digital advertising. Using a qualitative content analysis approach, ten advertisements were selected from YouTube channels of established brands and other available channels analysed according to the six-template framework: pictorial analogy, extreme situation, consequences, competition, interactive experiment, and dimensionality alteration.

The findings reveal that Extreme Situation and Consequences templates are the most frequently used creative structures in digital advertisements. Sports brands tend to emphasize exaggerated performance narratives, while household product brands rely more on emotional storytelling and social messaging. The study concludes that despite the transformation of advertising platforms due to digital media, the fundamental structures of creative advertising remain relevant in contemporary digital marketing.

Keywords: advertising, creativity templates, digital advertising, visual communication digital marketing

Introduction:

Advertising is an essential component of modern marketing communication that enables organizations to promote products, build brand identity, and influence consumer behaviour. build brand identity, and influence consumer behaviour. In competitive markets, creative advertising plays a crucial role in capturing audience attention and enhancing message recall (Belch & Belch, 2018). Traditionally, creativity in advertising has been viewed as an unpredictable process driven by artistic ideas. However, research suggests that many successful advertisements follow identifiable creative structures.

Goldenberg, Mazursky, and Solomon (1999) proposed the **Creativity Templates Theory**, which suggests that effective advertisements often follow specific patterns known as creativity templates. Their study identified six templates commonly used in high-quality advertisements: pictorial analogy, extreme situation, consequences, competition, interactive experiment, and dimensionality alteration.

With the rapid growth of digital media platforms such as YouTube, advertising strategies have evolved significantly. Despite these changes, the fundamental creative structures used in traditional advertising may still influence modern digital advertisements. Therefore, this study

examines the relevance of creativity templates in contemporary digital advertising by analysing selected advertisements from YouTube channels.

Literature Review:

Creativity has long been recognized as a fundamental component of effective advertising. Creative advertisements not only capture consumer attention but also enhance message comprehension and brand recall. According to Belch and Belch (2018), creativity in advertising plays a critical role in differentiating products and building strong brand communication strategies. Advertisements that incorporate unique storytelling, visual appeal, and emotional engagement are more likely to influence consumer attitudes and purchasing decisions.

Earlier research often treated advertising creativity as a spontaneous process driven by intuition and artistic inspiration. However, scholars later began to explore whether creativity in advertising could be understood through systematic frameworks. Smith and Yang (2004) argue that advertising creativity involves both originality and relevance, suggesting that effective advertisements must present novel ideas while maintaining a clear connection to the brand message.

Digital advertising has expanded significantly with the growth of online and social media platforms, enabling brands to reach audiences more effectively (Chaffey & Ellis-Chadwick, 2019). Social media platforms have become important channels for brand communication and digital marketing strategies (Tuten & Solomon, 2017).

One of the most influential theoretical frameworks explaining structured creativity in advertising is the **Creativity Templates Theory** developed by Goldenberg, Mazursky, and Solomon (1999). Their research analysed numerous award-winning advertisements and

found that highly creative advertisements often follow a limited set of recurring patterns known as creativity templates.

Their research identified six fundamental templates commonly found in successful advertisements:

1. **Pictorial Analogy** – presenting a product by visually comparing it with another object.
2. **Extreme Situation** – exaggerating a situation to emphasize product benefits.
3. **Consequences** – illustrating the positive or negative results of using or not using a product.
4. **Competition** – highlighting comparison between competing brands or products.
5. **Interactive Experiment** – demonstrating the product through an experiment or audience interaction.
6. **Dimensionality Alteration** – altering physical dimensions or perspectives to create surprise.

This framework challenged the traditional belief that creativity is entirely unpredictable and demonstrated that creative ideas often emerge from structured problem-solving approaches.

Further studies have emphasized the importance of storytelling and emotional engagement in advertising. Dahlen, Lange, and Smith (2010) suggest that narrative-driven advertisements are particularly effective in creating memorable brand experiences. Emotional appeals, relatable characters, and socially relevant messages can significantly enhance audience engagement and brand perception.

With the rapid expansion of digital media, advertising practices have evolved significantly. Platforms such as YouTube, Instagram, and other social media channels have transformed how brands communicate with consumers. Digital advertising allows for greater interactivity, visual storytelling, and audience participation (Kotler & Keller, 2016). Despite these technological

advancements, many researchers argue that the fundamental principles of creative advertising remain consistent across traditional and digital media environments.

Therefore, examining how creativity templates operate in contemporary digital advertisements can provide valuable insights into whether traditional creative frameworks continue to influence modern advertising strategies.

Objectives of the Study:

1. To understand the concept of creativity templates in advertising.
2. To examine the presence of creativity templates in selected digital advertisements on YouTube.
3. To identify which creativity templates are most commonly used in contemporary digital advertising.
4. To analyse how different brands apply creativity templates in their advertising strategies.
5. To evaluate the relevance of traditional creativity templates in the context of modern digital advertising.

Research Questions:

This study seeks to address the following research questions:

1. What creativity templates are used in selected digital advertisements on YouTube?
2. Which creativity templates are most frequently used in contemporary digital advertising?
3. How do different brands apply creativity templates in their advertising strategies?

Research Methodology:

1 Sampling Method:

The present study adopts a **qualitative content analysis approach** to examine the use of creativity templates in digital advertising.

Ten advertisements were selected from the **YouTube channels where Nike and Surf Excel** were available, using purposive sampling. These brands were selected because they are known for strong storytelling-based advertising campaigns.

2 Unit of Analysis:

The unit of analysis in this study is an individual advertisement. Each selected advertisement was examined based on its visual narrative, message structure, and storytelling elements to identify the creativity template used. Each advertisement was viewed multiple times and analysed according to the **Creativity Templates framework proposed by Goldenberg, Mazursky, and Solomon (1999)**.

The six creativity templates used for analysis include:

- Pictorial Analogy
- Extreme Situation
- Consequences
- Competition
- Interactive Experiment
- Dimensionality Alteration

The data were organized into tables the analysis was conducted using descriptive frequency analysis to identify the most dominant creativity templates used in the selected advertisements.

Data Analysis:

Data Source: Selected brands advertisements available on YouTube.

Table 6.1: Selection of Advertisements

Ad No.	Brand	Advertisement Title	Advertisements Links
1	Nike	Da Da Ding Campaign	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=2YDrgoRpic8
2	Surf Excel	Rang Laaye Sang (Holi Campaign)	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Zq7mN8oi8ds
3	Surf Excel	Keep India Clean	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=oh5U_dBA4Oo
4	Nike	Make It Count	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=WYP9AGtLvRg
5	Nike	Why Do It	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=iLL53TJN8LM
6	Surf Excel	Power of Ten Hands	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=E2C1Imr4dNw
7	Nike	Make the World Listen	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=-CW-K5x6zQc
8	Surf Excel	Ready for Life	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=TNNrV7zHm-Q
9	Nike	Make Every Yard Count	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=VjdAqXqYwm0
10	Surf Excel	Gokul Easy Wash	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=vcM-LLUKwW4

Table 6.2: Coding Scheme for Creativity Templates

For systematic analysis, each advertisement was coded according to the six creativity templates

proposed by Goldenberg, Mazursky, and Solomon (1999). The coding scheme used in this study is presented in Table 8.2

Table 8.1: Selection of Advertisements

Code	Creativity Template	Description of Template	Key Indicators in Advertisement
CT1	Pictorial Analogy	Product is visually compared with another object or concept.	Visual metaphor, symbolic comparison, resemblance between product and another object.
CT2	Extreme Situation	Product benefits are demonstrated through exaggerated or extreme scenarios.	Dramatic actions, exaggerated performance, unrealistic but impactful situations.
CT3	Consequences	Advertisement focuses on the results of using or not using the product.	Cause-effect storytelling, emotional or social outcomes shown in narrative.
CT4	Competition	Product is shown competing with another product, person, or situation.	Direct or indirect comparison, rivalry, superiority of brand.
CT5	Interactive Experiment	Advertisement involves demonstration or experiment showing product effectiveness.	Testing situations, experiments, audience engagement.
CT6	Dimensionality Alteration	Physical or conceptual dimensions of objects are changed to create surprise.	Change in size, perspective, or reinterpretation of familiar objects or slogans.

Table 6.3: Advertisement-wise Template Identification:

Ad No.	Brand	Advertisement Title	Creativity Template Code	Creativity Template
1	Nike	Da Da Ding Campaign	CT2	Extreme Situation
2	Surf Excel	Rang Laaye Sang (Holi Campaign)	CT3	Consequences
3	Surf Excel	Keep India Clean	CT3	Consequences
4	Nike	Make It Count	CT2	Extreme Situation
5	Nike	Why Do It	CT6	Dimensionality Alteration
6	Surf Excel	Power of Ten Hands	CT2	Extreme Situation
7	Nike	Make the World Listen	CT4	Competition
8	Surf Excel	Ready for Life	CT3	Consequences
9	Nike	Make Every Yard Count	CT2	Extreme Situation
10	Surf Excel	Gokul Easy Wash	CT3	Consequences

Table 8.3: Advertisement-wise Template Identification

Table 6.4: Frequency Analysis of Creativity Templates

Sr. No.	Creativity Template	Code	Number of Ads	Percentage
1	Extreme Situation	CT2	4	40%
2	Consequences	CT3	4	40%
3	Competition	CT4	1	10%
4	Dimensionality Alteration	CT6	1	10%
5	Pictorial Analogy	CT1	0	0%
6	Interactive Experiment	CT5	0	0%

Total Advertisements Analysed = 10

Table 8.4: Frequency Analysis of Creativity Templates

Interpretation:

The frequency analysis shows that Extreme Situation and Consequences templates dominate digital advertising, each representing 40% of the selected advertisements. Sports brand advertisements such as Nike primarily rely on the Extreme Situation template to emphasize performance, motivation, and athletic intensity. In contrast, Surf Excel advertisements mainly use the Consequences template, focusing on emotional storytelling and social messages.

The Competition and Dimensionality Alteration templates appear less frequently, while Pictorial Analogy and Interactive Experiment were not observed in the selected advertisements. This suggests that contemporary digital advertisements tend to emphasize narrative-driven storytelling rather than visual metaphors or experimental demonstrations.

Results & Discussion:**Key findings:**

The analysis of the selected advertisements revealed several important findings regarding the use of creativity templates in digital advertising.

1. **Extreme Situation and Consequences templates were the most frequently used,**

each accounted for 40% of the analysed advertisements

2. Advertisements from **Nike primarily used the Extreme Situation template**, presenting dramatic and high-intensity scenarios to highlight athletic performance, motivation, and determination.
3. **Surf Excel advertisements mainly used the Consequences template**, focusing on emotional storytelling and social outcomes rather than direct product promotion.
4. The **Competition template and Dimensionality Alteration template appeared only once** in the selected advertisements, indicating limited usage in the analysed sample.
5. The templates **Pictorial Analogy and Interactive Experiment were not observed** in the selected advertisements, suggesting that contemporary digital advertisements rely more heavily on **narrative storytelling and emotional engagement**.

These findings indicate that traditional creativity templates continue to influence advertising strategies in the digital media environment.

The findings of this study demonstrate that creativity templates remain relevant in contemporary digital advertising. Although digital platforms provide new technological capabilities such as animation, interactivity, and personalized targeting, the fundamental structure of creative advertising remains consistent.

Video advertising on platforms such as YouTube relies heavily on storytelling techniques that resonate with viewers. The **Extreme Situation** template effectively captures attention through dramatic visuals, while the **Consequences** template engages viewers through emotional narratives.

Indian brands such as Surf Excel, Zomato, and Amul frequently incorporate social messages

and storytelling in their advertising campaigns. These advertisements emphasize cultural values, social harmony, and everyday experiences, which resonate strongly with audiences.

The study also highlights the role of visual creativity in digital advertising. Video platforms allow brands to combine cinematography, animation, sound design, and storytelling to produce engaging advertisements. However, despite these technological advancements, the creative strategies used in advertising continue to reflect structured frameworks similar to those identified in earlier research.

Implications of the Study:

The findings of this study provide useful insights for advertisers, marketers, and media professionals. Understanding creativity templates can help advertising agencies develop structured creative strategies for digital platforms. Brands can use these templates to design more engaging video advertisements that effectively capture audience attention and enhance brand recall. The study also contributes to academic research in advertising and visual communication by demonstrating that traditional creative frameworks remain relevant in the digital advertising environment.

Conclusion:

The transformation of advertising media from traditional platforms to digital environments has significantly changed how brands communicate with consumers. Online video platforms such as YouTube allow advertisers to reach global audiences through creative storytelling and visually engaging content.

This study examined the relevance of creativity templates in digital advertising by analysing YouTube advertisements from various brands. The findings indicate that traditional

creativity templates continue to play an important role in contemporary advertising strategies.

Despite technological advancements and changes in media platforms, the fundamental principles of creative advertising remain consistent. Structured creativity frameworks such as the creativity templates proposed by Goldenberg, Mazursky, and Solomon provide valuable insights into the design and analysis of effective advertisements.

Future research may expand this study by analysing larger samples of advertisements across multiple digital platforms or examining audience responses to different creativity templates.

Limitations of the Study:

Although the study provides useful insights into creativity templates in digital advertising, it has certain limitations. First, the research analysed a **limited sample of ten advertisements**, which may not fully represent the wide variety of digital advertising campaigns available on online platforms. Second, the study focused only on **YouTube advertisements**, while other digital platforms such as Instagram, Facebook, and OTT services also play a significant role in digital marketing.

Another limitation is that the research used **qualitative content analysis**, which primarily focuses on identifying creative patterns rather than measuring audience responses. The study did not include audience surveys or engagement metrics such as likes, shares, or comments that could further explain the effectiveness of creativity templates in digital advertising.

Despite these limitations, the study provides a valuable framework for understanding how structured creativity is applied in contemporary digital advertisements.

Scope for Future Research:

Future studies can expand this research in several ways. Researchers may analyse **larger samples of advertisements across multiple digital platforms** such as Instagram, Facebook, and TikTok to gain a broader understanding of creativity in digital marketing.

Another potential direction is to conduct **audience perception studies** to examine how different creativity templates influence consumer attention, emotional engagement, and brand recall. Quantitative methods such as surveys or experimental studies could help measure the effectiveness of specific advertising strategies.

Additionally, future research may explore the role of **animation, artificial intelligence, and interactive technologies** in shaping creative advertising formats. As digital advertising continues to evolve, understanding the relationship between creativity frameworks and emerging media technologies will become increasingly important.

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